

Synthesis and Biocidal Activity Studies on Solid Complexes of Iron(II, III), Cobalt(II, III) and Nickel(II) with Violuric Acid and Dinitrosoresorcinol

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Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Co^{3+} and Ni^{2+} -violurate (VA) and -dinitrosoresorcinolate (DNR) complexes have been synthesised and screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities along with violuric acid, dinitrosoresorcinol metal salt $(NH_4)_2SO_4 \cdot FeSO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$, $FeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$, $CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Na_3[Co(NO_2)_6]$, $(NH_4)_2SO_4 \cdot NiSO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$ solutions. It was found that most of the compounds possessed fairly good antibacterial and antifungal activities and the growth inhibition of the studied bacteria and fungi species enhanced with the increase of violuric acid or dinitrosoresorcinol concentration in the complexes except Co^{3+} -DNR where the activities towards bacteria and fungi species decreased with the increase of [DNR]. However, the presence of uncomplexed active hydroxyl and nitroso groups attached to the resorcinol ring system is probably responsible for decreasing activity of these compounds.

In recent years, there has been intensive activity involving the synthesis and evaluation of the biological activities of heterocyclic nitrogen and/or sulphur ring containing compounds, and their derivatives and complexes¹.

Biochemical, pharmacological and medicinal significance of many coordination complexes have been studied and discussed. Iron has a vital functional role in living systems, i.e. oxygen-transport and electron-transfer. The best known biological function of cobalt is its intimate involvement in the coenzymes related to vitamin B₁₂² which is synthesised by bacteria³. Nickel has some undisclosed function in living organisms⁴ which can activate a number of metals *in vitro* bound to ribonucleic acids, and is found in blood, having a special affinity for bone and skin and plays important role in pigmentation. Dinitrosoresorcinol and its derivatives⁵ and violuric acid and its derivatives⁶ as well as their chelates were screened for their antibacterial action and are used in medicine.

The present work aims to study the effect of the metal salt ligands and metal chelates under study as fungicides and bactericides.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade (99.9%, B.D.H., Merck or Riedel). The isolated solid complexes of Fe^{2+} -VA(1:2), Fe^{3+} -VA(1:1, 1:2, 1:3), Co^{2+} -VA(1:1, 1:2), Co^{3+} -VA(1:1, 1:2, 1:3), Ni^{2+} -VA(1:1), Fe^{2+} -DNR(1:1, 1:2), Fe^{3+} -DNR(1:1, 1:2, 1:3), Co^{2+} -DNR(1:1, 1:2), Co^{3+} -DNR(1:1, 1:2, 1:3) and Ni^{2+} -DNR(1:1, 1:2) were prepared by refluxing a mixture of aqueous metal salt and ethanolic ligand

solutions (except Fe^{2+} -VA and Fe^{2+} -DNR complexes), and then evaporating to small volumes followed by the addition of acetone, diethyl ether or benzene. The resulting solid chelates were filtered, washed several times with the precipitating solvents and dried.

Biological activities of the complexes as well as violuric acid, dinitrosoresorcinol and their metal salts $(NH_4)_2SO_4 \cdot FeSO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$, $FeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$, $CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Na_3[(NO_2)_6]$, $(NH_4)_2SO_4 \cdot NiSO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$ were tested against bacteria and fungi species. In the present study, the sample (100 mg) of each of the chelates, violuric acid, dinitrosoresorcinol or metal salt were dissolved in ethylene glycol (1 ml) and kept for 48 h to get saturated. Filter paper plates (or bulbs) of 6 mm dia were placed over the saturated solutions and left for 48 h to transfer the samples into the filter paper plates. The test bacteria and fungi species were inoculated and then grown on nutrient agar (beef extract, 10 g dm⁻³; pepton, 5 g dm⁻³; NaCl, 5 g dm⁻³; agar, 15 g dm⁻³; pH, 7.1) and Czapeck's agar ($NaNO_3$, 3 g dm⁻³; K_2HPO_4 , 1 g dm⁻³; $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, 0.5 g dm⁻³; KCl, 0.5 g dm⁻³; $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, 0.01 g dm⁻³; sucrose, 30 g dm⁻³; agar agar, 15 g dm⁻³; pH, 6.4) media, respectively, for 10 days. Sterilised water (10 ml) was added to the cultures. Aliquots (1 ml) of bacteria and fungi spore suspensions were added to nutrient agar (for bacteria) and Czapeck's agar (for fungi) petri dishes, then the filter paper discs containing the test compounds were placed directly after the inoculation of the organisms. The inhibition zones formed around each filter paper after inoculation for 24 h at 37° in the case of bacteria and 4-7 days at 28° in the case of fungi species, were measured and the activities recorded.

TABLE 1—ANTIFUNGAL AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITIES OF METAL SALTS, VIOLURIC ACID AND METAL-VIOLURATE*

Organism	Activity (zone of inhibition)**																
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)	(14)	(15)	(16)	(17)
(A) Bacteria species																	
<i>Serratia</i> Sp.	+	-	-	-	-	-	++	+	++	++	+	+	+	-	+	-	+
<i>Bacillus stearothermophilus</i>	+	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	++	++	++	+	+	-	+	-	+
<i>Bacillus subtilus</i>	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	++	++	++	++	++	++	-	+	-	+
<i>Pseudomonas</i> Sp.	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	++	++	++	++	+	+	-	+	-	+
(B) Fungi species																	
<i>Aspergillus</i> Sp.	+	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	-	+	-	+
<i>Penicillium</i> Sp.	+	+	+	-	+	-	++	++	++	++	+++	++	++	-	+	-	+
<i>Alternaria</i> Sp.	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	++	++	+++	++	++	-	+	-	+
<i>Cirvularia</i> Sp.	+	-	-	-	+	-	++	++	++	+++	++	+	+	-	+	-	+

* (1) Violuric acid, (2) $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (3) $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (4) $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (5) $\text{Na}_2[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$, (6) $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (7) $\text{Fe}^{2+} - \text{VA} (1:2)$, (8) $\text{Fe}^{2+} - \text{VA} (1:1)$, (9) $\text{Fe}^{2+} - \text{VA} (1:2)$, (10) $\text{Fe}^{2+} - \text{VA} (1:3)$, (11) $\text{Co}^{2+} - \text{VA} (1:1)$, (12) $\text{Co}^{2+} - \text{VA} (1:2)$, (13) $\text{Co}^{2+} - \text{VA} (1:3)$, (14) $\text{Co}^{2+} - \text{VA} (1:1)$, (15) $\text{Co}^{2+} - \text{VA} (1:2)$, (16) $\text{Ni}^{2+} - \text{VA} (1:1)$, (17) $\text{Ni}^{2+} - \text{VA} (1:2)$. **Inhibition: (++++)=Very high, (+++)=high, (++)=moderate, (+)=poor, (-)=no effect.

TABLE 2—ANTIFUNGAL AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF METAL CHELATES OF DINITRORESORCINOLATE*

Organism	Activity (zone of inhibition)**												
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)
(A) Bacteria species													
<i>Serratia</i> Sp.	-	++	+	+	++	++	+++	++	++	-	+	++	-
<i>Bacillus stearothermophilus</i>	-	++	+	+	++	++	+++	++	++	-	+	++	+
<i>Bacillus subtilus</i>	-	++	+	+	+	++	+++	++	++	-	+	+	+
<i>Pseudomonas</i> Sp.	-	++	+	+	++	++	++	++	+	-	+	+	+
(B) Fungi species													
<i>Aspergillus</i> Sp.	-	++	+	+	++	++	+++	++	++	-	+	++	++
<i>Penicillium</i> Sp.	-	++	+	+	++	+++	+++	++	++	-	++	+	+
<i>Alternaria</i> Sp.	-	++	+	+	++	++	+++	++	++	-	++	++	+
<i>Cirvularia</i> Sp.	-	++	+	-	+	+	++++	+++	++	-	+	++	++

* (1) Dinitrosoresorcinol, (2) $\text{Fe}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:1)$, (3) $\text{Fe}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:2)$, (4) $\text{Fe}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:1)$, (5) $\text{Fe}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:2)$, (6) $\text{Fe}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:3)$, (7) $\text{Co}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:1)$, (8) $\text{Co}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:2)$, (9) $\text{Co}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:3)$, (10) $\text{Co}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:1)$, (11) $\text{Co}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:2)$, (12) $\text{Ni}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:1)$, (13) $\text{Ni}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:2)$. **Explanation same as in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The results (Tables 1 and 2) indicate that nearly all the synthesised chelates exhibit considerable activities, greater than those of the metal salts and ligands ; and only $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}^{2+} - \text{VA} (1:1)$, $\text{Co}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:1)$, $\text{Ni}^{2+} - \text{VA} (1:1)$, $\text{Ni}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:1)$ for bacteria, $\text{Ni}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:2)$ for fungi, and DNR have been found to be biologically inactive for bacteria and fungi species tested. Inactivity of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ may be ascribed as being nitrogen and sulphur (sulphate) source nutrients for bacteria and fungi ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are involved in the composition of media for fungi). $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ increases the chloride ion concentration in the media (NaCl in the case of bacteria and KCl in the case of fungi media) which is

responsible for osmotic pressure regulation of extracellular fluids, for photosynthesis and for growth of bacteria and fungi species. $\text{Co}^{2+} - \text{VA} (1:1)$ and $\text{Co}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:1)$ complex solutions still contain chloride ion. $\text{Ni}^{2+} - \text{VA} (1:1)$ and $\text{Ni}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:1)$ contain sulphur as sulphate. $\text{Ni}^{2+} - \text{DNR} (1:1, 1:2)$ complexes involve uncomplexed (free) NO and OH groups which may form $\text{N}=\text{O} \cdot \text{H}-\text{O}-$ linkage in addition to the peptide linkage which depress the activity of these complexes towards the fungi and bacteria. Inactivity of DNR may be related to the same reason ($-\text{N}=\text{O} \cdot \text{H}-\text{O}-$ and peptide linkages). $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution exhibits very poor activity against *Bacillus subtilus*, *Pseudomonas* Sp., *Penicillium* Sp. and *Alternaria* Sp. and inactive towards other organisms. $\text{Na}_2[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ solution shows very poor antimicrobial activity for the test fungi and *Bacillus subtilus*

and *Bacillus stearothermophilis*, and inactive against *Serratia* Sp. and *Pseudomonas* Sp. Poor activity or inactivity of $\text{Na}_2[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ and $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ towards the bacteria and fungi species may be attributed to its involvement with NO_2^- (as nutrient) or Cl^- (essential for the growth of bacteria and fungi) ions or due to the bioactive action of Co^{3+} or Fe^{3+} ions.

Violuric acid shows a promising effective antimicrobial activity (inhibitor) against all the test bacteria and fungi species, while dinitrosoresorcinol does not show significant effect (inactive). Therefore, the extent of antibacterial and antifungal activity induced by violuric acid and its complexes are higher than those induced by dinitrosoresorcinol and its complexes. The non-toxic nature of the free dinitrosoresorcinol may be due to the strong *ortho* and *para* directing influence of phenolic hydroxyl group; the reactivity of the phenol depends upon the number of *ortho* and *para* positions. Besides, the presence of $\text{N}=\text{O}$ group affects the orientation of the OH groups and causes deactivation (overgrowth) of dinitrosoresorcinol towards bacteria and fungi. Also, the non-toxic (inactive) nature of dinitrosoresorcinol may be attributed to the presence of two OH and $\text{N}=\text{O}$ groups in positions different than in violuric acid, where they have the possibility to form $-\text{N}=\text{O} \cdots \text{H}-\text{O}-$ linkage as evident from the structures of the compounds.

Fe^{2+} -VA(1:2) complex exhibits significant antibacterial and antifungal activities indicating that the complex is more active compared to violuric acid and Fe^{2+} solutions. This increase in activity may probably be due to a comparatively faster diffusion of the metal complex as a whole through the organisms, due to its more liposoluble nature on being coordinated with the metal ion forming stable metal chelates⁶.

Generally, the biocidal activity of the metal chelates are considerably higher as compared to that of the metal ions and ligands. The inhibition of fungal and bacterial growth rate increases gradually with the increase of ligand concentration in the complexes (complexes of higher M:L ratios are more active than the lower ones). The increase may also probably be attributed to the combined bioactive effects of metal and ligand present in the

complex and trace elements present in bacteria and fungi species due to breaking the peptide linkage, due to their liposoluble nature as being coordinated with metal ions forming stable metal complexes or due to that the metal violurate and dinitrosoresorcinolate complexes have comparatively faster diffusion as a whole through the cells of bacteria and fungi, which is in accordance with the earlier observations⁷. On the other hand, the antigrowth (inhibition) of the tested fungi and bacteria species may be due to the exchange of trace metals of the metalloenzymes (present in the cell fluids and responsible for the growth) with the metal ions of the complex under test forming new complexes with extra stability or the trace metals of the metalloenzymes react with the test complexes and form mixed metal complexes. This may bring about a change in the nature of activities of enzyme, amino acids, carbohydrate, etc. (blocking synthesis of these active materials)⁸.

Another explanation is that the metal complexes and metalloenzymes (present in the cellular fluids of the microorganisms) react and form multienzymatic complexes which may serve as catalysts capable of improving and achieving reactions in the living organisms yielding to stunt or inhibit growth. Activity of high molecular weight complexes (containing higher ratios of ligands) may be ascribed as being more encumbered and bulky which allow a very important steric control (cage or open-well effect) during the complexes approach. This leads to increase the violurate complexes activity and slightly decrease the dinitrosoresorcinolate complexes activity (due to the increase of hydroxyl groups) towards the bacteria and fungi species.

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